

A Study on Employee Satisfaction of Meenatchi Hospital Employees in Thanjavur

P. Sakalya

MBA student, Department of Management Studies,
Periyar Maniammai Institute of Science and Technologies, Vallam, Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' well satisfied with their job, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Employee satisfaction can be measured in cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. This paper deals with the satisfaction level of employee at MEENAKSHI hospital. The Primary data was collected through a questionnaire distributed in meenakshi hospital with a sample size of 305. Statistical tools used for analyze is chi-square and descriptive statistic. This paper revealed that salary package through the employees is highly satisfied.

Keywords: Chi-square, Descriptive statistics, satisfaction, employees, working environment, Salary, Communication

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1. INTRODUCTION

Employee satisfaction is the individual employee general attitude towards the job. It also an employee cognitive and affective evaluation of employees job. Employee satisfaction is a comprehensive term that comprises job satisfaction of employees and their satisfaction overall with company's policies, company environment and etc. Satisfaction based on employees needs from the company. A satisfied employee normally works with ability and performing to their best. Employees are main part of the process of achieving the mission and vision of a company. Mostly satisfied employees are most involved to the work that the dissatisfied employee. Employees are considered to be one of the most important pillars on which the building of organization stand. there are various factors that contribute

to employee satisfaction, it includes treating employees with respect, time to time performance appraisals, providing regulars employee recognition, empowering employees, relationship with immediate supervisor, providing employee perks, company activities, positive management within a success framework of goals, feeling safe in the work environment ,opportunities to use skills and abilities, compensation and benefits, promotions, training, work task factors, relationship with co-workers, relationship with supervisors. Having good relationship with the colleagues, high salary, good working conditions, training and education opportunities, career development or any other benefits may be related with the increasing of employee satisfaction

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ganesha Acharya and Abbokar Siddiq (2018) studied the satisfaction level among the employees looking at working conditions, Grievance handling systems, Relationship with Colleagues, Reward systems, Welfare Facilities, Promotion and Career Development opportunities, Job Security Provisions, Personal factors & other factors at Adam sugar mills. The sample size was 120. Data was collected through simple sampling random method. The statistical tool used was chi-square test. The result revealed that good work environment, good reward and good work conditions can increase employee job satisfaction.

Khalil-Ur Rahman, et.al (2017) examined the job satisfaction of sales agents from Islamic and conventional insurance of Pakistan. The sample size was 318. Data was collected through multi-stage stratified random sampling. The statistical tool were used multiple regression and hierarchal regression model including 11 hygiene-motivational. The result revealed that was, Job satisfaction is any blend of mental, physiological, and natural circumstances that bring about a man honestly to say I am satisfied by my job.

KhurramShahzad, er.al (2017) calculated the mediating impact of job satisfaction on the relationship in Pakistan. The sample size was 190. Data was collected through simple random sampling method. The statistical tool used for research was Correlation Analysis, Descriptive Statistics, regression. The Results showed that Job satisfaction can be achieved through effective implementation of compensation plans and managing workload.

Subhasish Chatterjee, SmritiPriya (2016) studied on employee satisfaction in Multi specialty Hospital in Mumbai. The sample size was 105. The data was collected through simple random sampling methods. The statistical tool were used, percentage analysis and U- test. The results shows that, most of the employees are satisfied with the management and with their supervisor

SomayahSalahshouriArdestani (2017) studied on employee satisfaction and during this process to understand the psychology-employee behavior in Hyderabad-India. The sample size was 200. Data was collected through simple random sampling method. The statistical tool was used chi-square test. The results show that, if the performance (hospitals Services) falls short of expectations, the employee is dissatisfied and if it matches the expectations, the employee is satisfied.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the overall job satisfaction of the employees in meenakshi hospital
- To know the communication effectiveness between supervisor and employees

3.2 VARIABLE

Dependent variable : Employees
 Independent variable :satisfaction, hospital, working environment, salary, communication level, long term plan, leave policy, training , job secure, co-workers, working condition,

3.3 HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no relationship between Employees and management
 H1: There is significant relationship between Employees and management.

3.4 AREA OF STUDY

This study is based on the analysis of employee’s satisfaction at meenatchi hospital Thanjavur.

3.5 DATA COLLECTION DESIGN

This study mainly based on primary data. The primary data was collected from Meenakshi hospital employees through structured questionnaires. And the secondary data was collected from some journals, books.

3.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Simple random sampling method was used

3.7 STATISTICAL TOOL USED

Descriptive analysis
 Chi-square

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

- To know the overall satisfaction

Descriptive statistics

S. No	VARIABLES	MEAN
1	understand the long-term plan	3.62
2	leadership to implement the plan	3.96
3	adequate planning of hospital objectives	4.15
4	contribute to the planning process	4.39
5	proud to work for the Hospital	4.25
6	contribute to the facility’s plan and mission	4.35
7	enough authority to make decisions I need to make.	3.64
8	physical working conditions are good	4.42
9	If I do good work I can count on doing extra work	4.29
10	If I do good work I can count on being promoted	4.29
11	I believe my job is secure	3.86
12	feel part of a team working toward shared goals	4.20
13	I like the type of work that I do	4.16
14	I feel valued at Hospital	3.93
15	like the people I work	4.15
16	I experience a spirit of cooperation	4.23
17	I am treated like a person, not a number	4.12
18	recognition by management for work that’s well done	4.39
19	Communications from management are frequent enough	4.26
20	Communications from management keep me up to date on the hospital	4.29
21	I feel I can trust what I am told by the management staff	4.90
22	Quality is a top priority at the Hospital	4.27
23	help to make decisions	4.23
24	supervisor gives me adequate support	4.21
25	supervisor treats me with respect	3.87
26	I feel that my supervisor treats me fairly	4.23
27	supervisor tells me when my work needs to be improved	4.19
28	enough information by the Hospital to do my job well	4.26
29	initial training provided by the Hospital was as much as I needed	4.19
30	ongoing training as I need is provided by the Hospital	4.16
31	believe my salary is fair for my responsibilities	4.45
32	would recommend employment at the Hospital to my friend	4.29
33	Overall benefits package	4.26
34	Sick leave policy	4.12

INTERPRETATION

The findings of the study indicates that salary is fair for my responsibility as shows that the higher mean of 4.45.the respondents also agreed that physical working condition is good the mean value is 4.42.and contribute to the planning process the mean value is 4.39. This table also indicates that understand the long-term plan lower mean 3.62.

CHI-SQUARE TEST

To know the relationship between employees and management

	VALUE	DF	ASYMPTOTIC SIG(2-SIDED)
PERSON CHI-SQUARE	17.280	4	.002
LIKEHOOD RATIO	20.992	4	.000
LINEAR-BY-ASSOCIATION	7.079	1	.008
NON VALID CASES	305		

INTERPRETATION

Chi-square test shows that significant value less than 0.05, thus we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative (H1).there is association relationship between employees and management. Since the p-value = .008 which is greater than the table value, accepted the null hypothesis.

5. FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION FINDINGS:

It is observed from the study that the meenakshi hospital employees are well satisfied to working at the working environment(physical condition) .They organizing food is too hygienic healthy to the patients and workers to work, the working time also perfect for the workers, salary of the workers is completely comfortable. There is a good relationship between employees and management they are giving training to the employees for learning, growth and personal development of the employees.

SUGGESTION:

All the features are enough for the workers, but they need some entertainment to refresh themselves. Women employees need the hostel facility inside the hospital for women employee safety.

CONCLUSION:

The study helped in revealing the level of satisfaction of employees with reference to Meenakshi Hospital Employees. This research revealed that the factors of employee's satisfaction level of employees. From this research it is observed that majority of the employees were satisfied in their work. it has been found out that two three variables one is salary package (4.45), physical working condition (4.42) and contribute to the planning process(4.39).The communication level is also high according to the table value(chi-square).

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